

Araa Smart Mobile Application

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Abstract:

Our system is a banking application. Titled Araa Smart Mobile Application. The idea is to provide a smart mobile application to help the blind category to perform the various tasks that is offered by banks in Oman. Araa as we mention before it aims to facilitate banking operations for this category. One of the main services that our application provides the voice services. For example, if the blind wants to log in, the application gives instructions to him by saying (please say 1 to log in and please say 2 for a new user), so the blind person chooses one of the verbally operations by say the number of the operation, and the application moves to the operation that he chose. The proposed Araa Smart Mobile Application would support voice commands to support many services include login, registration, check balance, adding new accounts, transfer from one account to another account and pay bills. This reasons that we the current banks mobile applications don't provide any support for the blind category. The software's that we will use to create our application are python, C# and Html5. We believe in the future, our application will be widely used by the blind due to its ease of use, and blind people do not need help from another person.